

EVALUATING DISCIPLINARY PROCESS AND IMPLICATION FOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS ADMINISTRATION ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN NASARAWA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study evaluates disciplinary process and implications for secondary schools administration on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State. The study employed descriptive survey research design. This is because survey research design is an effective vehicle to collect data from samples representing large populations. The population of the study comprised of teachers, principals and Students in all public secondary schools Nasarawa State. Through randomly sampling technique, 510 respondents were selected from 10 schools for the study (10 principals, 100 teachers and 400 students respectively). The data collection instrument was a self-developed questionnaire. The questionnaire had two sections. Section A of the questionnaire covered the demographic data of respondents, while section B consisted of structure questionnaire according to the research objectives. The instrument was subjected to experts in educational administration and measurement and evaluation. Their comments and observations led to restructured of the instrument for precision. Therefore, a validity index of 0.86 was obtained. Through pilot study, a reliability coefficient of 0.78 was established for the research instruments. This implies that the instrument was reliable for use. In analyzing the data collected for the study, the mean and standard deviation were used to answer research question, while the hypotheses formulated were tested using the t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that punishment play significant roles in enhancing students' academic performance by making sure that students follow school rules and regulations. It was concluded that students should not be left out in formulation of rules and regulations and decision-making process on matters that affect them even though they are key stakeholders in schools. Based on the findings, it was recommended that a system should be planned by head of schools whereby members from best performing secondary schools have an opportunity to meet frequently to share experiences on discipline-related matters vis-à-vis academic achievement among other recommendations.

Keywords: Evaluating, Disciplinary Process, Implication, School Administration, Academic Achievement

Introduction

Students' indiscipline in schools which portrays itself in the form of crime, violence, strikes and disorderliness have become major international issues as reported in various national surveys of school order and safety (Evertson, 2022). These problems not only endanger students and teachers but also impedes proper implementation of curriculum. Discipline is the orderly manner in which members of an organization organize themselves in reference to set rules and objectives. It is the ability of the members to strive towards one set

objective. School unrests caused by high indiscipline, has been captured as an international phenomena that has hindered major educational achievements.

In recent years, the problem of school discipline has become an important problem for school leaders. This is a result of the emergence of bad behaviour among secondary school students. Anti-social behaviour is personal behaviour that violates social norms, harms others, and disregards others, whether intentionally or not, rather than the behaviour that is beneficial to people. Hyman (2018) has it that crime harms other people. Some of the bad behaviours that occur by middle school students include damaging school property, using bad language, bullying or mocking, harassment, violence, torture, theft, etc. Byarugaba (2021) remarked that in the contemporary Nigerian society those good characters are degraded. In recent years, mischief has increased in many public and private schools. Peer violence, bullying, violence in teacher-student relationships, harassment, prostitution, theft, cheating in examinations, damaging, etc.

These traits were not the needed trait to produce good graduates and successful leaders in the future.

Discipline in the classroom is a prerequisite if any meaningful learning is to take place and that no meaningful learning can take place in a chaotic environment (Galabawa, 2021; Ohsakio, 2017). They further observed that of all the activities that comprise the role of the teacher, classroom discipline is one of the most significant. The teacher's role is made more problematic when classrooms and schools become unmanageable. "Teachers may waste special teaching time trying to settle disciplinary problems" (Galabawa, 2021). The issue of learner indiscipline has taken center stage for a long time internationally and nationally. In the United Kingdom, for example, there are reports of many cases of classroom disorder. Learners are generally noisy, rowdy and disrespectful to educators (Porteus, 2021).

Effective discipline helps in the achievement of goals, expectation and responsibility in students (Haller, 2017). Good discipline creates a good image of the school and prepares learners for the future. Disruptive behavior amongst learners eliminated if there is good discipline at school. The implementation of effective discipline at school is a key for the learner in his journey to adulthood. By definition discipline refers to the ability to carry out reasonable instructions or orders to reach appropriate standards of behaviors. It is understood to be that abstract quality in a human being which is associated with and manifested by a person's ability to do things well at the right time, in the right circumstance, without or with minimum supervision (Nyaga, 2017).

There is extensive evidence describing students' discipline as being related to the students' characteristics (Kajubi, 2017; Hyman et al., 2018). However, beyond the students' characteristics, the school characteristics are important constructs which determine the propensities of students to embrace discipline (Evertson et al., 2022; Gyamera 2015). One of such school characteristics is the school administrative information (SAI). For instance, the design and structure of the SAI exemplifies the acceptable and non-acceptable behaviours within the school settings (Haller, 2017). However, the central role of the SAI is scarcely discussed in the empirical literature. And in the marginal evidence available, the emphasis is hardly on the specific component of SAI as it may correlate with the students' discipline levels. This paper therefore relies on the notion that a well-packaged, student-focused SAI goes a long way in instilling discipline among the students opportunities offered to them. Canter (2020) argues that it is difficult to maintain order and discipline in schools where teachers have no space to sit, prepare and mark students' work. In other words, Mtsweni (2018) supports the above scholars that availability of teaching and learning materials has an impact on school discipline.

Indiscipline in schools, and consequently, school strikes, destroy the teaching- learning environment. Occasionally there are protests, riots and violence and sometimes the police have to come in to intervene to protect school property. Some schools become virtual prisons as they construct huge walls and expensive fences to protect good students, teachers and property against undisciplined students. Freire et al (2019) argues that violence is a sensitive issue that provokes anxiety, arouses emotions has negative impact on school achievement.

Research in other country has proven that various factors related to secondary school principals are major causes of student disturbances (Adams, 2013). Researchers also observed that poor management skills by heads of institutions of learning lead to cases of indiscipline (Adesina, 2014). This was approved by Mirit (2022), who pointed out that indiscipline in Nigerian secondary schools was associated with unclear and unfair school rules. With the introduction of free education for all (EFA) and universal basic education (UBE) in Nigeria, there have been increased enrolment figures in schools. This has resulted in overcrowded classes and increased challenges for teachers to deliver effective teaching and learning, necessitating increased discipline enforcement. Premature engagement in gender issues, leading to unwanted pregnancies and early marriage, is on the rise among students in schools. The possession of cell phones has also become a significant concern.

Furthermore, indiscipline among students in schools has resulted in numerous instances of uncontrolled school outgoing and incoming behavior. These bad mannerisms end in school dropouts and poor academic achievement. For several years now there have been concerns by various people and groups regarding the deterioration of the quality of education in secondary schools. Schools vary in categories, some school have maintained standard other school standard decline. It's time to look the circumstances surrounding differential performance among them; as well as the varying levels of discipline associated with different school categories. This study focuses on evaluating of disciplinary process and implications for secondary schools administration on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

It is obvious that students are priceless assets and most essential elements in education. It is absolutely necessary to direct students to exhibit acceptable attitude and behaviour within and outside the school. In an attempt to achieve an organized and peaceful school environment and maintain law and order, school managements should specify rules and regulations to guide the activities of members of the educational organization. In Nasarawa State where discipline is a serious problem in secondary schools, causing the students in question to be smoking, prostitute, steal, involve cultism, indecent dressing and other social vices. Some troublesome students sometimes make teachers react emotionally to the extent of using punishment which does not discourage misbehavior, but rather reinforces the students' view of adult as treacherous. This study therefore, intends to evaluate disciplinary process and implications for secondary schools administration on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to evaluate disciplinary process and implication for secondary school administration on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State. Specifically the objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine the suitability of set rules and regulations in best and least discipline schools and students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State.

2. Examine the mechanisms in place that ensures students' abides to prescribed rules and regulations and their academic achievement in Nasarawa State.
3. Establish how students punishment and management influence students' academic performance in Nasarawa State.
4. Investigate how the administration of school rules and regulation Contribute to students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State.

Research Questions

The study answered the following research questions.

- i. To what extent does set of rules and regulations in best and least discipline schools affect students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State?
- ii. What is the mechanism in place to ensure that students' abides to prescribed rules and regulations and their academic achievement in Nasarawa State?
- iii. What is the extent of students' punishment and management influence on academic achievement in Nasarawa State?
- iv. What is the extent of administration of school rules and regulations contribute to students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- i. There is no significance difference between the suitability of set of rules and regulations in best and least discipline school and students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State.
- ii. There is no significance difference between the mechanism in place that ensure students abide to prescribed rules and regulations and academic achievement in Nasarawa State.
- iii. There is no significance difference between students' punishment and management influence and students' academic performance in Nasarawa State.
- iv. There is no significance difference between the administration of school rules and regulations and students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State.

Methodology

This study employed descriptive research design. This is because survey research design is an effective vehicle to collect data from samples representing large populations. The population of the study comprised of teachers, principals and Students in all public secondary schools in Nasarawa State. Through randomly sampling technique, 510 respondents were selected from 10 schools for the study (10 principals, 100 teachers and 400 students respectively). The data collection instrument was a self-developed questionnaire. The questionnaire had two sections. Section A of the questionnaire covered the demographic data of respondents, while section B consisted of structure questionnaire according to the research objectives. The instrument was subjected to experts in educational administration and measurement and evaluation. Their comments and observations led to restructured of the instrument for precision. Therefore, a validity index of 0.86 was obtained. Through pilot study, a reliability coefficient of 0.78 was established for the research instruments. This implies that the instrument was reliable for use. In analyzing the data collected for the study, the mean and standard deviation were used to answer research question, while the hypotheses formulated were tested using the t-test at 0.05 level of significance. However,

since the rating of the instrument was on a 4 point, the mean (x) of 2.50 was used for taking decision such that mean (x) rating on the item equal or to or above 2.50 was regarded as 'Agree' and mean (x) rating less than 2.50 was regarded as 'Disagreed'.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent does set of rules and regulations in best and least discipline schools affect students’ academic achievement in Nasarawa State?

Table 1: Mean score of respondents’ responses of principals, teachers and Students onset rules and regulations in best and least discipline schools and student academic achievement.

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD
1	Ensuring the school curriculum is designed and implemented in accordance with the National Policy on Education,	3.90	.33
2	School rules and regulations are integrated with school policy to control the school discipline	3.07	.38
3	School policy provides clear guidelines for action that should be consistently applied	3.35	.89
4	School has availability of physical resources and conducive environment for learning to help the set rules.	2.49	.96
5	School has good leadership style and apply consistence punishment rules to offender	3.82	.48
6	School had clear rules and regulations that is suitable to deal with school discipline issues	3.07	.41
7	Monitoring curriculum delivery to guarantee Student bullying disorder in classrooms	3.33	.98
8	Monitoring curriculum delivery to punished Student disrespect for teachers.	2.53	1.01
9	Observing classroom instruction to ensure alignment with policy objectives and quality teaching practices	3.83	.53
10	Supporting teachers in implementing innovative teaching strategies to improve student learning outcomes.	3.04	.40

The data presented in Table 1 revealed that, all items have impacts on set rules and regulations in best and least discipline schools for student academic performance because each of the items have means score above the cut-off score of 2.5 except item 4 with mean = 2.49 and std = .96. Item 1 has highest mean = 3.99 and std. =.33. Also, item 9 with mean = 3.83, and std. = .53. Followed by item 5 has mean = 3.82 and std. = .48 and so on. This implies all the listed items except item number 4 are set rules and regulations in best and least discipline schools have impact on students’ academic achievement in Nasarawa State.

Research Question 2: What are the mechanisms in place to ensure that students’ abides to prescribed rules and regulations and their academic achievement in Nasarawa State?

Table 2: Mean score and SD of the responses on mechanisms in place to ensure that students' abides to prescribed rules and regulations and their academic achievement.

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD
1	Students should be involved in the formulation of school rules	3.78	.52
2	Once the rules are created, it should be communicated to the students and also post on the notice board of the school	3.04	.37
3	Regular meeting should be held between principal teachers, and students to discuss school rules	3.28	.92
4	Students should be consulted when major decisions affecting them are made	2.48	.99
5	Guidance and counseling services should be given to students on a regular basis	3.79	.52
6	Students should have freedom to seek assistance from teachers when faced with problems	3.06	.34
7	Students and teachers who violate the school rules should be punished openly	3.18	.91

Table 2 revealed that item 5 has highest impact with mean and standard deviation of 3.79 and .52 respectively. This was followed by item 1 and 3 with their means and standard deviations of (3.78, .52), and (3.28, .92) respectively. All the items have scores above the cut-off mark except item4 with mean = 2.48 and std. = .99. This clearly shows that respondents agreed to those items as mechanisms that need to put in place to ensure that students' abides to prescribe rules and regulations to enable them have good academic achievement in Nasarawa State.

Research Question 3: What is the extent of students' punishment and management influence on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State?

Table 4: Mean score of respondent's responses on extent of students' punishment and management influence on academic achievement.

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD
1	Punishment management at school increase attendance and influence student academic performance	3.40	.57
2	Punishment increase respect to teachers and other students	3.52	.58
3	Punishment make student come to school on time	2.79	.61
4	Punishment make students avoid drinking, smoking and fighting	3.04	1.29
5	Punishment make student keep quit on the absence of teachers	3.35	.54
6	Punishment led respect for school property	3.53	.58
7	Enforcing rules and regulations by taking disciplinary actions against offenders	2.86	.67
8	Issuing school rules and regulation booklets for students to read	3.00	1.29
9	Punishment through suspension, expulsion etc.	3.41	.55
10	Orientation of new students in line with school rules and regulations	3.52	.56

All the 10 items in Table 3 have their means above the cut-off score. Leading the table with highest mean and standard deviation was item 10 (3.52, .56), followed by item 2 (mean =3.58, std. = .52) and item 9 (mean = 3.41, std. = .55). There is clear evidence that all respondents agreed to those items as extent of students’ punishment and management influence on students’ academic achievement in Nasarawa State.

Research Question 4: What is the extent of administration of school rules and regulations contribute to students’ academic achievement in Nasarawa State?

Table 4: Mean score of respondent’s responses on the extent administration of school rules and regulations contribute to students’ academic achievement.

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD
1	The school administration ensures that student arrive at school on the opening day of school to enable them meet up with the school work.	3.38	.55
2	The school administration ensures that students have copy of school rules and regulation every term	3.58	.57
3	The school administration are strict on students permission before leaving school ground	2.81	.62
4	The school administration ensures that students do all classes and school activities.	3.10	1.32
5	Administration of school rules and regulations enable students and teachers to be in their best behaviour.	3.29	.57
6	School rules and regulations are strategies designed to instill good conduct to the students which implies self-control, orderliness, acceptable behavior and obedience to the school authority	3.61	.60
7	Rules and regulations are set to maintain proper governance and build respect among the teachers and the students	2.81	.62
8	School rules, and regulations are effective in remediating one’s misbehavior and therefore improving the school’s order	3.06	1.32
9	School rules, and regulations serve as motivators to improve students’ sense of responsibility and intellectual ability	3.73	.62
10	School rules and regulations were found to be reliant on the parental upbringing and social environment as intervening variables.	3.29	.64

Data presented in Table 4 above showed that all the 10 Items had their mean ratings above the cut-off point of 2.50. Therefore, the respondents agreed with these items as the extent to which administration of school rules and regulations contribute to students’ academic achievement in secondary schools in Nasarawa State.

Testing Research Hypotheses

H01 There is no significance difference between the suitability of set of rules and regulations in best and least discipline school and students’ academic achievement in Nasarawa State.

Table 6: t-test Analysis of Principals and Teachers’ mean rating of the suitability of set of rules and regulations in best and least discipline school and students’ academic achievement.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	Std.	Df	T	p-value
Principal	10	27.20	6.49	98	-4.50	.001
Teachers	90	33.01	3.49			

*p<0.05

Table 5 shown that $t = -4.50$ at $df = 98$ and $p < .05$. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative. This implies that there is significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and teachers regarding the suitability of set of rules and regulations in best and least discipline school and students’ academic achievement in Nasarawa State.

H0₂ There is no significance difference between the mechanism in place that ensures students abide to prescribed rules and regulations and students’ academic achievement in Nasarawa State.

Table 7: t-test Analysis of Principals and Teachers’ mean rating on the mechanism in place that ensure students abide to prescribe rules and regulations and students’ academic achievement.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	Std.	Df	T	p-value
Principal	10	27.20	5.31	98	-5.44	.001
Teachers	90	33.01	3.58			

*p<0.05

Table 6 shown that $t = -5.44$ at $df = 98$ and $p < .05$. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative. This implies that there is significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and teachers regarding the mechanism in place that ensure students abide to prescribe rules and regulations and academic achievement in Nasarawa State.

H0₃ There is no significance difference between students’ punishment and management influence and students’ academic achievement in Nasarawa State.

Table 7: t-test Analysis of Principals and Teachers’ mean rating of the student punishment and management influence and students’ academic achievement.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	Std.	Df	T	p-value
Principal	10	27.20	5.89	98	-5.10	.001
Teachers	90	33.01	3.79			

*p<0.05

Table 7 shown that $t = -5.10$ at $df = 98$ and $p < .05$. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative. This implies that there is significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and teachers regarding the student achievement and management influence and students’ academic achievement in Nasaraw State.

H0₄ There is no significance difference between the administration of school rules and regulations and students’ academic achievement in Nasaraw State.

Table 9: t-test Analysis of Principals and Teachers’ mean rating on the administration of school rules and regulations and students’ academic achievement.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	Std.	Df	T	p-value
Principal	10	27.20	6.11	98	-6.44	.001
Teachers	90	33.01	4.28			

*p<0.05

Table 8 shown that $t = -6.44$ at $df = 98$ and $p < .05$. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative. This implies that there is significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and teachers regarding the administration of school rules and regulations and students’ academic achievement in Nasarawa State.

Discussion of Findings

The study showed that most of the set school rules and regulations used in the schools were suitable in managing school discipline contrary to least performing schools where they were well written but not well executed as a result many discipline problems were observed. From the finding the reasons and factors behind violating of school rules and regulations were associated with shortage of teachers and teaching learning materials, overcrowded classes, poor housing, delayed services such as of teacher salary payment, and the absence of libraries and laboratories. Other factors like leadership style were bureaucracy in decision making and lack of consistency in decision implementation. These factors, at the time of study, were either absent or minimal in most secondary schools. This was evidenced by the research conducted by Ajayi et al (2019), who found that school code of conduct, student motivation, mindset interventions, social belonging and goal setting are the key determinant in shaping students’ academic outcomes and well-being as well.

The study findings as regards mechanisms in place to ensure that students’ abides to prescribed rules and regulations in other to help their academic performance in Nasarawa State shows that majority of the respondents are in agreement that students should be involved in the formulation of school rules, once the rules are created, it should be communicated to the students and also post on the notice board of the school, regular meeting should be held between principal teachers, and students to discuss school rules and students should have freedom to seek assistance from teachers when faced with problems. The above findings are aligned with the findings in the study by Harris (Hyman et al, 2018), who found that school set rules and regulations for the proper governing of the various styles of students intend to promote order and efficiency in the school and hence promote students’ academic performance.

The study findings revealed that punishment play significant roles in enhancing students’ academic performance by making sure that students and teachers follow school rules and regulations. In school punishment was fair and it was consistence applied. One the other hand, the study finding shows that punishment management at school increase attendance and influence student academic performance as well as make students avoid drinking, smoking and fighting. The findings above aligned with the study of Byarugaba (2021), who found that instructional strategies including rules and regulations and interventions aimed at enhancing students’ achievement, particularly through cooperative learning structure.

The findings from the respondents on the extent administration of school rules and regulations contribute to students’ academic performance shows greatly that School rules, and regulations are effective in remediating one’s misbehavior and therefore improving the school’s order, serve as motivators to improve students’ sense of

responsibility and intellectual ability and also rules and regulations were found to be reliant on the parental upbringing and social environment as intervening variables. The findings above aligned with the study of Evertson (2022) who revealed that most of the students that were part of his study understand that punishments, school rules, and regulations are effective in remediating one's misbehavior and therefore improving the school's order. He also added that the following serve as motivators to improve students' sense of responsibility and intellectual ability.

Conclusion

Students should not be left out in formulation of rules and regulations and decision-making process on matters that affect them even though they are key stakeholders in schools. Their participation should not be seen to cause undue pressure to the school management, administrators, teachers and parents. When students are treated or seen as minor, immature and inexperienced to make independent decisions on matters of the school and are viewed as problematic. This renders them passive, as decisions that concern them are made on their behalf either by their teachers, parents or administrators. The communication between students and school administration influences students' discipline. Effective Communication between students, teachers and school administration reduces conflicts which may result into indiscipline that may cause confrontations. Principals should encourage open door policy should be encouraged in school to compact the indiscipline cases. The findings indicated that administrators' enforcement of rules and regulations, management of peer pressure, involvement of students in decision-making, controlling the use of social media information and principal mode of communication influence student discipline in secondary schools.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

1. A system should be planned by head of schools whereby members from best performing secondary schools have an opportunity to meet frequently to share experiences on discipline-related matters vis-à-vis academic performance. Their mutual understanding can be expected to help both sides to look into and act upon the variables that weaken their sides.
2. The government, in collaboration with community local authorities, should exert more effort aimed at motivating teachers through adequate and timely salary payments, improved conditions of service, availability of teaching-learning materials and improved school infrastructure. This gesture can only raise teachers' self-esteem and the status of the teaching profession, leading to a reduction in the malpractices that negatively impact on school discipline and academic performance.
3. Parents and teachers are the most powerful influence on the child's life experiences, especially on educational outcomes. There should be parent -teacher relations so as to control indiscipline among students in school. To this effect, parent-teacher associations (PTAs) should be established by head of schools as a matter of policy for all schools, where some parents could be elected as "school representatives" within the community.
4. Since students are targeted beneficiaries of school rules and academic interventions, there is a need for management of both categories of schools to devise ways of involving the students more in matters relating to formulation and implementation of school rules and regulations for an effective non-oppressive school discipline.

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